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Fertility restoration studies in four WA CMS lines of rice

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Fertility restoration studies involving four wild abortive (WA) cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines—V20A, IR58025A, IR62829A, and IR54752A—resulted in the identification of 20 restorers. We studied segregation for fertility in the F₂ and backcross progenies of these CMS lines with four restorer lines—ARC11353, IR30864, IR13419-113-3, and IR9761-19-1. The results indicated that fertility restoration in WA CMS lines was controlled by two additive major genes. Their effect was sporophytic and they displayed differential gene interactions such as epistasis with complete dominance (12:3:1) or epistasis with incomplete dominance (9:6:1) depending on the parents involved in the cross.

We noticed differential segregation of the F₂ and backcross progenies in the crosses involving IR30864 and IR9761-19-1 depending on the female parent. This suggested that the performance and expressivity of the R genes varied according to the nuclear background of

the female parent. The pattern of segregation in crosses involving IR54752A was different from that of other CMS lines, suggesting the involvement of certain minor genes for fertility restoration carried by this CMS line in deciding the fertility of the progenies. ■

Effect of minor genes in restoration of fertility in CMS lines of rice

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We evaluated 128 hybrids in the 1994 dry season and 135 hybrids in the 1995 wet season. The hybrids, involving varieties C29 and PMK2, with different wild abortive (WA) sources of cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines—IR58025A, IR62829A, and PMS3A—showed marked differences in pollen and spikelet fertility. When C29 was crossed with IR62829A and PMS3A, it behaved as a partial restorer (21-90% pollen and spikelet fertility). But when crossed with IR58025A, it behaved as a maintainer (100% pollen and spikelet sterility). All three CMS lines, however, had WA cytoplasm. Similarly, PMK2 behaved as a restorer (>90% pollen and

spikelet fertility) with PMS3A, while it maintained sterility (100%) with IR62829A. The minor or modifier genes present in the pollinator might have reacted with the CMS lines used and resulted in this type of variation. ■

Breeding for male fertility restoration incorporating Basmati rice quality

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Basmati is the most highly valued rice commodity in the world agricultural trade market. Pusa Basmati 1, released in India, combines both high yield and ideal Basmati quality. In Pakistan, semi-tall Pak 385 and Pak 386 are reported to be better yielding than Basmati 370. Results at IARI have demonstrated the possibility of developing hybrids with Basmati grain quality and a high level of heterosis. Such Basmati hybrids would raise yields further.

A major limitation to developing Basmati rice hybrids is the nonavailability of satisfactory restoration among Basmati cultivars or breeding lines. Some 90% of Basmati materials showed imperfect maintaining ability, 3%